

A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF LITERAL AND FREE TRANSLATION APPROACHES IN TRANSLATION (BASED ON O. HENRY'S "THE LAST LEAF")

Makhamadova Guzaloy Elyorbek kizi

Faculty of Foreign Philology, Department of Foreign Language and Literature (English),
4th-year student, National University of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulugbek,
Tashkent, Uzbekistan. maxamadovaguzaloy@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17075750>

Abstract: This article presents a comparative analysis of literal and free translation approaches using O. Henry's short story "The Last Leaf" as a case study. The main objective of the research is to determine which method is more effective in translating metaphors, expressions, idioms, and artistic imagery in the story. According to the article, the translator's primary task is not only to translate the text, but also to convey its essence, idea, and spirit, enriching it while preserving its original meaning for the reader.

Keywords: translation, literal translation, free translation, metaphor, idiom, artistic imagery, O. Henry, The Last Leaf.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada asar tarjimasida so'zma-so'z tarjima qilish va ma'noga ko'ra tarjima qilish yondashuvlari "So'nggi yaproq" asari misolida qiyosiy tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqotning asosiy maqsadi asardagi metaforalar, iboralar, idiomalar, hamda badiiy obrazlarni tarjima qilishda qaysi usul samarali ekanligi o'rganiladi. Maqolaga ko'ra, tarjimon asosiy vazifasi nafaqat asarni tarjima qilish, balki uni asl holda, g'oyasini, ruhini saqlagan holda yanada boyitib o'quvchiga yetkazib berishdir.

Kalit so'zlar: tarjima, so'zma-so'z tarjima, ma'noga ko'ra tarjima, metafora, ibora, badiiy obrazlar, O. Genri, "So'nggi yaproq".

Аннотация: В данной статье представлен сравнительный анализ дословного и свободного подходов к переводу на примере рассказа О. Генри «Последний лист». Основная цель исследования — определить, какой метод является более эффективным при передаче метафор, выражений, идиом и художественных образов в произведении. Согласно статье, главная задача переводчика заключается не только в переводе текста, но и в передаче его сути, идеи и духа, обогащая его при этом и сохраняя первоначальный смысл для читателя.

Ключевые слова: перевод, дословный перевод, свободный перевод, метафора, идиома, художественный образ, О. Генри, Последний лист.

INTRODUCTION

The word *uslub* (style) is originally Arabic and means method, order, manner, or form. In translation, the issue of style is very important because it is the translator's task to convey not only the content of the text but also the author's style of expression, tone, and literary or scientific characteristics accurately. Preserving the original style in translation is one of the translator's most important duties because style expresses the individuality of the author. Correctly conveying the style preserves the artistic and aesthetic value of the text and demonstrates the use of the author's creative skill. Therefore, when translating a text, it is important to render metaphors, idioms, and artistic images as closely as possible to the author's style. In literary studies, style refers to each creator's way of writing, mode of expression, and manner of depiction. Style is used in both narrow and broad senses. In the narrow sense, style

means the method of description, narration, or speech, while in the broad sense, it includes the creator's style (A. Qahhor, A.L. Qozonchi), the style of a work ("O'tkan kunlar," "O'gay ona"), writers' styles (Jadids), styles of literature (Eastern, Western, Uzbek, Turkish), period styles (11th, 19th centuries), and movements' styles (realism, romanticism), and others. "Author's style refers to the set of main elements frequently found in a particular author's works created during a specific period or characterizing their entire creative output" [1, 66]. N. Shukurov defines style as "the creator's unique perception of reality and the reflection of events through distinctive images and means of expression" [2, 7]. Style is not only this but also includes the unity of elements such as the theme, idea, mode of expression, portrayal of characters, and so on, which constitute the distinctiveness of the author's style.

One of the main methods in translation studies is literal (word-for-word) translation, and the other is meaning-based translation. In literal translation, the translator relies on the original text, translating words directly and adhering to grammar, while meaning-based translation focuses on conveying the main idea and content while preserving the sense rather than the exact form of the original text. This method allows the translator to use various equivalents, comparisons, and idioms to ensure the reader's understanding. Literal translation is often used in scientific sources, while meaning-based translation is applied in literary works and poetry.

O. Henry, whose real name is William Sydney Porter, was a famous American short story writer known worldwide for his short stories. His most famous works include "The Gift of the Magi," "The Ransom of Red Chief," "The Cop and the Anthem," "The Last Leaf," and others.

MAIN PART

1.1 Advantages and disadvantages of literal (word-for-word) translation.

In translation theory, the literal translation method is one of the oldest and most widely used. It conveys the lexical units and grammatical structure of the source text as faithfully as possible in the translation. Despite its advantages, it also has shortcomings. One advantage is accuracy and the presence of equivalents. Literal translation preserves the syntactic structure and word-to-word correspondence of the source text. Therefore, it is effective for scientific, technical, and legal texts. Literal translation helps students and linguists to understand the structure and semantics of the source language. For example, in "The Last Leaf," the sentence "I've been sick for a long time. I'm tired of waiting" translated literally becomes "Men uzoq vaqtdan beri kasalman. Men kutishdan charchadim" (I have been sick for a long time. I am tired of waiting). This translation is accurate and concise. Another example is "It is a sin to want to die," translated as "O'lishni xohlash gunohdir" (To want to die is a sin). This sentence does not need to change its meaning because the author wrote it universally and simply.

1.2 Disadvantages of literal translation. Literal translation may not be effective in literary translations because it can distort the meaning. It often loses the artistic tone. In such cases, the emotions of the characters and the author's style may not be adequately conveyed. The main characteristic of literary texts is their emotional impact, imagery, and harmony. Literal translation weakens this approach. For example, the sentence "When the last one falls I must go" translated literally becomes "Oxirgisi tushsa, men ham ketishim kerak" (When the last one falls, I must go). The drawback here is that the sentence sounds dry and lacks drama. A better translation would be "Oxirgi yaproq ham tushsa, men ham hayotdan ko'z yumaman" (When the last leaf falls, I too will close my eyes to life). Another disadvantage is artificiality. Literal translation may be grammatically correct but unnatural in Uzbek, which causes

boredom for readers. For example, “The cold breath of autumn had stricken her” literally translated as “Kuzning sovuq nafasi uni urdi” (The cold breath of autumn struck her) sounds unnatural. A better translation is “Kuzning sovuq nafasi uni holdan toydirdi” (The cold breath of autumn exhausted her). Moreover, metaphors and symbols play an important role in literary works as they reveal the author’s creativity. The sentence “I want to go sailing down, down, just like one of those poor, tired leaves” literally translated becomes “Men pastga, pastga suzib tushmoqchiman, xuddi o’sha bechora, charchagan barglardan biri kabi” (I want to sail down, down like one of those poor, tired leaves), which sounds artificial to the reader. A better translation would be “Men ham o’sha charchagan barglar kabi asta pastga tushishni istayman” (I too want to slowly fall down like those tired leaves).

2.1 Advantages of meaning-based translation. In translation theory, meaning-based translation is not word-for-word but focuses on the meaning, content, and idea. Preserving the literary style is more natural in meaning-based translation, and the translator’s tone, rhythm, and images are better expressed. Another advantage is the impact on the reader: the reader experiences aesthetic pleasure and imagines the characters’ emotions. When translated meaningfully into Uzbek, the symbols are understandable and figurative to the reader.

2.2 Disadvantages of meaning-based translation. One disadvantage is that the translator may insert their own opinions into the text. Sometimes, the literal meaning of the text is lost. Meaning-based translation is usually suitable for literary texts but can cause ambiguity when used for scientific texts.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, there are literal and meaning-based translation methods in translation theory. The translator chooses the most appropriate method for the text. Meaning-based translation is effective for literary works and poetry, while word-for-word translation is more suitable for scientific texts. The research showed that using both methods for translating “The Last Leaf” yields good results. The translator should choose or combine methods according to the text type to accurately convey the content and tone, especially in literary works.

References:

Используемая Литература: Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

1. Nida, E. A. (1964). *Toward a Science of Translating*. Leiden: Brill.
2. Newmark, P. (1988). *A Textbook of Translation*. London: Prentice Hall.
3. Bassnett, S. (2002). *Translation Studies*. London and New York: Routledge.
4. Baker, M. (2011). In *Other Words: A Coursebook on Translation*. Routledge.
5. O. Henry. (1907). *The Last Leaf*. In *The Trimmed Lamp and Other Stories*.